

THE UNTAPPED POTENTIAL OF NATURAL DYEING AGENTS: INDIGENOUS FRUITS IN SUSTAINABLE FABRIC DYEING

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the potential of natural dyeing agents derived from indigenous fruits, specifically mango, bignay, and achuete, to produce high-quality dyed fabrics. An experimental research design was employed, wherein each fruit underwent three treatment variations based on quantity. Purposive sampling included diverse participants from the fashion industry, including students, instructors, and boutique owners. A survey questionnaire was utilized to assess the acceptability of dyed fabrics across several criteria: appearance, rubbing fastness, usefulness, eco-friendliness, and marketability. Statistical analysis using mean and two-way ANOVA revealed that mango and bignay consistently achieved "Highly Acceptable" ratings for their brightness, vibrancy, and colorfastness. In contrast, *bankoro* was found unacceptable, emphasizing the importance of selecting appropriate natural dye sources. The findings advocate for the integration of natural dyes in sustainable textile production, promoting local agricultural practices and encouraging further research into the commercial viability of these eco-friendly alternatives.

Keywords: *Natural dyes, Indigenous fruits, Fabric dyeing, Eco-friendliness, Sustainable textile production, Experimental research*

INTRODUCTION

Dyeing is an ancient art of human civilization. It is one of the earliest methods of coloring fabrics using plants, which were the primary sources of natural colorants during

the Greek and Roman periods. The *Vedas*, especially the *Atharveda*, contain descriptions of natural dyes, and the use of natural dyeing materials is evident in the wall paintings of Ajanta, Ellora, and Sithannavasal. These masterpieces still demonstrate the efficacy of the dyeing craft inherited from ancient times in India. As civilization has progressed, the dyeing process has evolved from natural to chemical methods.

Natural dyes are colorants derived from plants, invertebrates, or minerals. Most natural dyes are vegetable-based, and sourced from plant materials such as roots, berries, barks, leaves, wood, and other biological sources like fungi and lichens. Many natural dyes require the use of chemicals called mordants to bind the dye to the textile fibers; early mordants include tannin from oak galls, salt, alum, vinegar, and ammonia from stale urine. Many mordants, and even some dyes, produce strong colors, and large-scale dye works were often isolated in specific districts due to the odors and other byproducts associated with the dyeing process.

In a study by Tamburini et al. (2024), three main sources of red natural dyes and three main sources of yellow natural dyes were identified, namely for reds: cochineal, madder, and lac, and for yellows: larkspur, pagoda tree flower buds, and grape vine leaves, with cochineal and larkspur being the most common. Loum et al. (2021) efficiently dyed cotton yarns with a plant dye from ornamental mustard (**Brassica juncea**) using certain optimized variables. The dye extraction medium, wavelength, extraction time, and dyeing pH were standardized. Dhanania et al. (2021) successfully dyed cotton in various hues and tones, with and without mordants, using different concentration levels of baboon extract.

Despite the potential of plant-based dyeing, much of this industry remains underdeveloped. Due to limited technical knowledge on extraction and dyeing techniques, textiles dyed naturally may fade when exposed to sunlight, sweat, and air. Additionally, producing consistent shades with natural dyes can be challenging, as these agro-products vary across crop seasons, locations, species, and maturity levels (Savvidou & Economides, 2007).

Since the advent and commercialization of synthetic dyes, which replaced natural dyes, the use of natural dyes in textiles has been reduced substantially. However, with increasing environmental awareness, people are now more inclined toward using natural products due to their renewable nature, reduced environmental impact, and sustainability. This shift has revived interest in using natural dyes for textile materials.

This study was conducted to determine the acceptability of selected fruits as alternative sources of dyes. These fruits include coconut, mango, bignay (wild cherry), achuete (annatto), and bankers. The following sections provide essential information about these fruits.

The word "coconut" (or the outdated "cocoanut") can refer to the entire coconut palm, the seed, or the fruit, which is botanically a drupe and not a true nut. The only surviving species of the genus *Cocos* is the coconut tree (*Cocos nucifera*), which belongs

to the Arecaceae family of palm trees. The name coconut is derived from the old Portuguese word *coco*, meaning "head" or "skull," due to the three depressions that resemble facial features on the coconut shell. Coconut trees are a hallmark of the tropics and are commonly found in coastal tropical areas. Studies have shown the potential of extracting coloring dye from coconut fibers (Kholil et al., 2021; Kusumawati et al., 2021; Kasim et al., 2023; Putri et al., 2020).

Mangifera indica (MI), the scientific name for the mango, has been a key herb in traditional and Ayurvedic medicine for almost 4,000 years. Mangoes belong to the Anacardiaceae family of flowering plants, which includes roughly 30 species of tropical fruiting trees. The tree is large and green and is primarily valued for its ripe and unripe fruits. In India, approximately 500 varieties of mango are known. Beyond its edible fruit, mango leaves and fruit have been proven to be an alternative, eco-friendly natural dye for textiles (Ayele et al., 2020; Jabar et al., 2022; Ahsan et al., 2020).

Bignay, scientifically known as *Antidesma bunius*, is a beautiful, dioecious shrub or small tree that grows 4 to 10 meters high. It has small, glossy, dark green leaves with a pointed tip and a rounded or pointed base. The flowers are tiny, fragrant, and green. The fruit is small, juicy, tart, well-flavored, thin-skinned, round to ovoid in shape, and dark crimson when ripe. Each fruit has a single flat seed, with 20 to 25 fruits per cluster. Bignay grows in some Asian countries, including the Philippines, as well as in parts of Australia. The fruit can be used as a source of blue dye, while the leaves are sometimes used as a substitute for tomato or vinegar in fish and meat stews.

Bixa orellana, the scientific name for annatto or achuete, originated in tropical America and is widespread in the lowlands of the Philippines. It is a small, bushy tree that can grow 2 to 8 meters tall, with a stem color ranging from green to red. The leaves are heart-shaped, and the fruits range from deep red to green. Seed pods can be round, elongated, or pointed and dry to a brown color. They open to reveal seeds in colors from bright orange to yellowish red. The dried seeds (bixin) are used commercially for coloring butter, cheese, and other foods, as well as in leather and floor polish production.

Morinda citrifolia, commonly known as Bankoro, belongs to the Rubiaceae family of coffee plants. It is native to Australia and Southeast Asia. *Bankoro* is a small, erect shrub or tree that can reach a height of 15 feet and has spreading branches. Its leaves are large, oval, and bright green, with creamy white lateral veins. The fruit, which is as large as a child's fist, is meaty and has a pale yellow color when fully mature. Though the fruit has an unpleasant taste and odor, the leaves are medicinal, and the juice is used in a health drink called noni. The root bark of the plant is also used for dyeing in Java.

Based on the discussions above, this study hypothesizes that the concentrated liquid extracts from the selected fruits would be acceptable natural fabric dyes and may produce vibrant colors. Producing natural fabric dye from selected indigenous plants in the Philippines would not only promote sustainable livelihoods for agriculturists but also make the textile industry more competitive by reducing production costs and eliminating high expenses on imported chemicals. Additionally, this study aims to assist in the

recognition and identification of various pigments present in fruit extracts and to develop dyes that are both ecologically and economically feasible.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop natural dyeing agents out of indigenous fruits such as mango, *bignay* (wild cherry), *achuete* (annatto), coconut, and *bankoro*.

Specifically, the study shall answer the following questions:

1. What are the correct processes for extracting natural dyeing agents from selected fruits?
2. What are the FTIR lab results of the color fastness to laundering rating and colorfastness to rubbing rating of the fabrics dyed with mango, bignay, achuete, coconut, and *bankoro* fruit dyes?
3. What is the acceptability of the produced fruit dyes in terms of appearance, rubbing fastness, usefulness, eco-friendliness, and marketability?
4. Is there a significant difference between the evaluations of the three groups of respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Extraction of Natural Dyeing Agents from Mango, Bignay, Atchuete, Coconut, and Bankoro

Materials

The following materials were used in the extraction of dyeing agents from the collected fruits:

- Mango
- Bignay
- Atchuete
- Coconut
- Bankoro

The fabrics used in this study included:

- Wool
- Silk
- Cotton

Tools and Equipment

The following tools and equipment were used in conducting the study:

- Basin
- Casserole
- Strainer
- Bolo

- Measuring Cup
- Weighing Scale
- Stove/Gasul

Procedures

Preparation of Dyeing Agent

The following process was used to prepare indigenous dyeing materials from fruits:

1. Each type of fruit was washed separately and placed in a bowl to prepare for extraction.
2. The fruit material was placed in a large non-reactive pot (such as stainless steel or glass). The dye could stain some pots and spoons, so these items were dedicated to dyeing.
3. The pot was filled with twice as much water as plant material and brought to a boil.
4. The mixture was simmered for an hour or so until a dark color was achieved.
5. The plant material was strained out, and the liquid was returned to the pot.

Preparation of Fixative or Mordant

A fixative, or “mordant,” was prepared to help the fabric absorb the natural dyes more effectively. For berries, salt was used, while vinegar was used for other plant materials. The measurements were as follows:

1. Salt: ½ cup of salt was dissolved in 8 cups of cold water.
2. Vinegar: 1 part white vinegar was blended with 4 parts cold water.
3. Damp fabric was placed in the fixative solution for an hour and rinsed with cool water afterward.
4. The fabric was then ready for dyeing.

Preparation of Fabric for Natural Dyeing

Before starting the dyeing process, the fabric was washed but kept wet. The following steps were taken:

1. The fabric was carefully placed in the dye bath and brought to a slow boil, simmering for about an hour with occasional stirring.
2. The color was checked, noting that it would lighten when dried. An hour generally produced a nice color, but darker hues were achieved by leaving the fabric in the dye overnight.
3. Once the desired color was reached, the fabric was removed, dried as usual, and ironed.

Projected Production Cost of Natural Dyeing Agents from Fruits

Projected Production Cost of Natural Dyeing Agents from Fruits				
Ratio: 1 Kg Riped Fruit (Atchuete, Bankoro, Bignay, Coconut and Mango)				
Yield: 1 Yard Fabric (Cotton, Silk and Wool)				
Quantity	Unit	Description	Unit Cost	Total Cost
1 ½	Kg.	Mango	80	120
2	Pc	Young coconut	45	90
1 ½	Kg.	bignay	60	90
1 ½	Kg.	Bankoro		
300	Grams	Atchuete	20	120
1	Bottle	Cane vinegar	18	18
1 ½	Yard	Fabric (silk, cotton, wool)	80	120
TOTAL				558

Treatment, Preparation, and Process

The fruits were harvested, and the necessary equipment for cooking the fruits was prepared. For each set of fruits, one liter of water was boiled for the set time, then removed from the stove and allowed to cool in a basin. The fruit was then squeezed and filtered, and the extract was mixed and boiled with the fabric set. After boiling, the cloth was soaked for two hours, then hung and spread in the sun until it dried.

A. Mango Fruits

Treatment 1

- ¼ kilogram (250 grams) ripe mango
- 5x5-inch fabric (cotton, silk, and wool)

One liter of water was boiled in a casserole for ten minutes, and then ¼ kilogram of ripe mango was added, along with the fabric samples. The mixture was boiled for an additional 30 minutes and then soaked in a basin for two hours before being sun-dried.

Result:

This treatment was ineffective; the fabric did not retain color well, was scratchy, and the color was unappealing despite a sweet scent.

Treatment 2

- ½ kilogram (500 grams) ripe mango
- 5x5-inch fabric (cotton, silk, and wool)

With ½ kilogram of mango, the process was repeated.

Result:

This treatment was also ineffective. While the fabric smelled sweet, it was scratchier, and the color was still unappealing, similar to the first attempt.

Treatment 3

- ¾ kilogram (750 grams) ripe mango
- 5x5-inch fabric (cotton, silk, and wool)

The procedure was repeated with ¾ kilogram of mango.

Result:

This treatment was still ineffective. Although it smelled sweet, the fabric was scratchy, and the color was not appealing.

This pattern continues for each fruit type and each treatment, with each experiment being documented with treatment quantities, procedures, and results.

Research Design

This study employed an experimental method, which was appropriate as the research involved multiple processes to extract dye from the fruits. Each fruit underwent three different treatments, focusing on the quantity used in the dyeing process. The results were observed, compared, and evaluated based on the dyed fabrics produced from each treatment.

Sampling and Participants

The study employed purposive sampling to select participants, focusing on individuals with relevant experience and expertise in the fashion industry. Participants were chosen based on three main criteria: (1) knowledge, experience, and expertise in the fashion industry; (2) formal education in the field; and (3) recognition as a consumer

or as a prominent figure within the fashion industry, such as boutique owners, fashion designers, or dressmaking and tailoring shop owners and workers. Participants needed to meet at least one of these criteria to be included in the sample.

The sample consisted of three distinct groups. The first group included sixty (60) students officially enrolled in Garment and Fashion Design, Dressmaking, or Tailoring courses at the Isabela State University - City of Ilagan, San Mateo Campus during the first semester of the 2020-2021 academic year. The second group comprised twenty (20) garment and fashion design instructors, professors, and trainers from Isabela State University, along with selected trainers with formal education or training in garment technology. The third group consisted of forty (40) well-known boutique owners, fashion designers, and sewers from the province of Isabela. This sampling method ensured that the study gathered insights from diverse representatives within the fashion industry, providing a well-rounded and comprehensive perspective.

Data Gathering Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection in this study was a survey questionnaire. Two sets of questionnaires were developed by the researcher, based on related literature and prior studies, and were validated by experienced instructors and professors who served as panel members but were not participants in the study. One set of questionnaires was translated into the mother tongue, Ilocano, to facilitate responses from certain boutique owners, fashion designers, and dressmaking and tailoring shop owners and workers.

The survey questionnaire was specifically designed to assess the acceptability of dyed fabrics created with fruit dyes that underwent three experimental treatments, differentiated by fruit quantities of 0.25 ($\frac{1}{4}$), 0.5 ($\frac{1}{2}$), and 0.75 ($\frac{3}{4}$) kilos. Evaluation criteria included appearance, rubbing fastness (both warp and weft directions), usefulness, eco-friendliness, and marketability. The fabrics used in these experiments were silk, cotton, and wool, each evaluated across these parameters to determine the acceptability and potential value of fruit-dyed fabrics.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the campus administrator of ISU-San Mateo, the SMVIHS administrator, to administer the survey instrument to the faculty and students in the Garment and Fashion Design, Dressmaking and Tailoring courses at the Isabela State University City of Ilagan, San Mateo Campus. Likewise, the survey questionnaire was communicated to the boutique owners, fashion designers, tailoring shop owners, and workers. The experiment and evaluation were held in the garment room.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools used in analyzing and interpreting the data are the mean and ANOVA. The arithmetic mean was used to determine the single value as a representative of the whole distribution and provides an accurate description of the entire data set. On the other hand, a two-way ANOVA was used to determine the significant difference in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents with a 0.05% significance level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Laboratory Test Results for Colorfastness to Laundering Rating and Colorfastness to Rubbing Rating of Dyed Fabrics

CHEMICAL TESTING LABORATORY	
TEST REPORT	
Subject: Five (5) samples of fabric properly identified.	Req. Ref. No.: PTRI-012023-CHE-0014
<u>Sample Code</u>	<u>Customer's Description</u>
	<u>Dyed Fabric Sample using</u>
CHE-0051	Mango
CHE-0052	Atzaete
CHE-0053	Coconut
CHE-0054	Bignay
CHE-0055	Bankoro Fruit extracts

Test Requested	Test Results	
1. Colorfastness to Laundering, rating AATCC Test Method 61-2020: Test 1A, 40°C Launder-Ometer Testex TF418 AATCC Standard Reference Detergent WOB AATCC Gray Scales Multifiber Test Fabric #10	<u>Change in Color</u>	<u>Staining</u>
CHE-0051	Grade 1.5	acetate Grade 4.5 cotton Grade 4.5 nylon Grade 4.5 polyester Grade 4.5 acrylic Grade 4.5 wool Grade 4.5
CHE-0052	Grade 3.5	acetate Grade 4.5 cotton Grade 2.5 nylon Grade 4.5 polyester Grade 4.5 acrylic Grade 4.5 wool Grade 4.5
CHE-0053	Grade 2	acetate Grade 4.5 cotton Grade 4 nylon Grade 4.5 polyester Grade 4.5 acrylic Grade 4.5 wool Grade 4.5

Test Requested		Test Results			
1. Colorfastness to Laundering, rating (cont.)		<u>Change in Color</u>		<u>Staining</u>	
	CHE-0054	Grade 3.5		acetate	Grade 4.5
				cotton	Grade 4
				nylon	Grade 4.5
				polyester	Grade 4.5
				acrylic	Grade 4.5
				wool	Grade 4.5
	CHE-0055	Grade 2.5		acetate	Grade 4.5
				cotton	Grade 4.5
				nylon	Grade 4.5
				polyester	Grade 4.5
				acrylic	Grade 4.5
				wool	Grade 4.5
2. Colorfastness to Rubbing, rating AATCC Test Method 8-2016 SDL Atlas M238BB Electronic Crockmeter AATCC Gray Scale for Staining As-received sample		<u>Staining</u>			
		<u>Dry</u>		<u>Wet</u>	
	CHE-0051	Grade 4		Grade 1	
	CHE-0052	Grade 3.5		Grade 1	
	CHE-0053	Grade 4.5		Grade 3	
	CHE-0054	Grade 4.5		Grade 2.5	
	CHE-0055	Grade 4		Grade 2	

Table 1. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Mango in terms of Appearance using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	4.38	Highly Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	4.28	Highly Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	4.42	Highly Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	4.44	Highly Acceptable

Treatment 2	3.94	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	4.11	Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	4.08	Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.53	Acceptable
Treatment 3	3.87	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	3.98	Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	3.88	Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.73	Acceptable

Table 1 presents the acceptability of dyed fabric using mango in the different treatments. Based on the table above, the respondents had the same level of acceptability in the dyed fabric using mango in Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 with mean ratings from 3.53 to 4.11 or "Acceptable."

Furthermore, the respondents gave the highest satisfaction with the dyed fabric of mango using Treatment 1. These were based on the mean ratings from 4.28 to 4.44 or "Highly Acceptable."

Table 2. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bignay in terms of Appearance using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	3.96	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	4.01	Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	4.05	Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.88	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.71	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	3.47	Acceptable

2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	3.74	Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.74	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.54	Highly Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	4.51	Highly Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	4.60	Highly Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	4.60	Highly Acceptable

Table 2 presents the acceptability of dyed fabric using bignay in the different treatments. Based on the table above, the respondents had the same level of acceptability in the dyed fabric using bignay in Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 with mean ratings from 3.47 to 4.05 or "Acceptable."

Table 2 further revealed that the respondents highly recommended the bignay in producing dyed fabric using Treatment 3 with mean ratings from 4.51 to 4.60 or "Highly Acceptable."

Table 3. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Atchuete in terms of Appearance using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	3.83	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	3.77	Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	3.84	Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	4.44	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.77	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	3.76	Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	3.92	Acceptable

3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.53	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.19	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	4.30	Highly Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	4.28	Highly Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.73	Acceptable

Table 3 presents the acceptability level of dyed fabric using achuete in terms of appearance using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

The table revealed that the respondents had the same level of acceptability in Treatment 1 and Treatment 2. On the other hand, they had the highest level of satisfaction in Treatment 3, mainly, the dispersion of dyed in the material and the texture of the material.

Table 4. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Coconut in terms of Appearance using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	3.63	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	3.62	Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	3.75	Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.58	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.46	Acceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	3.43	Acceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	3.53	Acceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	3.34	Moderately Acceptable

Treatment 3	1.93	Unacceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	1.91	Unacceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	1.88	Unacceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	1.92	Unacceptable

Table 4 reveals the acceptability level the quality of dyed fabric made from coconut. The results revealed that the respondents satisfied from Treatment 1 to Treatment 2 with mean ratings from 3.34 to 3.63 or "Acceptable". However, the respondents were not satisfied with the results of dyed fabric using Treatment 3. These findings suggested that using Treatment 1 is more effective than other treatments in producing dyed fabric using coconut.

Table 5. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bankoro in terms of Appearance using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	1.52	Highly Unacceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	1.45	Highly Unacceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	1.52	Highly Unacceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	1.52	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 2	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 3	2.00	Unacceptable
1. Dye spread homogenously to the material.	2.00	Unacceptable
2. Dyed fabric's color brilliance and vibrancy.	2.00	Unacceptable
3. Dyed fabric is translucence and naturally glossiness.	2.00	Unacceptable

Table 5 presents the acceptability level of the respondents in dyed fabric using Bankoro. The results revealed that the respondents had similar level of satisfaction from Treatment 1 to Treatment 3. These were based on the mean ratings from 1.00 to 1.52 or “Highly Unacceptable.”

However, the respondents gave mean ratings of 2.00 or “Unacceptable” in Treatment 3. These results imply that the quality of dyed fabric using Treatment 3 was improved. Generally, the findings suggested that using Bankoro in producing dyed fabric is not highly recommended in terms of appearance.

Table 6. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Mango in terms of Rubbing Fastness (Warp and Weft Direction) using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	3.60	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	3.73	Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	3.58	Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.55	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.66	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	4.51	Highly Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	3.73	Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.65	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.16	Acceptable
4. Resistance to Fading.	4.45	Highly Acceptable
5. Resistance to Staining.	4.29	Highly Acceptable
6. Negligible Change.	3.73	Acceptable

Table 6 presents the level of acceptability of mango in producing dyed fabric using Treatments 1,2, and 3. The table indicated that the respondents had the same level of acceptability in using Treatment 1 and 2 except for one indicator with a mean rating of 4.51 or “Highly Acceptable” under Treatment 2. These findings suggest that Treatment 2 is more effective than other treatments in resisting fading.

Furthermore, Treatment 3 has a higher mean rating of 4.16 or "Acceptable" than the other treatments, indicating that it is the most productive in generating dyed fabric, particularly in terms of brightness and vibrancy of color.

Table 7. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bignay in terms of Rubbing Fastness (Warp and Weft Direction) using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	3.79	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	3.81	Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	3.86	Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.74	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.98	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	3.47	Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	4.13	Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.99	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.63	Highly Acceptable
7. Resistance to Fading.	4.51	Highly Acceptable
8. Resistance to Staining.	4.69	Highly Acceptable
9. Negligible Change.	4.62	Highly Acceptable

Table 7 presents the acceptability level of dyed fabric using bignay in terms of rubbing fastness or the warp and weft direction using Treatments 1, 2, and 3.

The respondents have the same level of acceptability in Treatments 1 and 2 with mean ratings from 3.47 to 4.13 or “Acceptable.” On the other hand, the respondents gave the highest mean rating of 4.63 in Treatment 3 or “Highly Acceptable.” The results imply that the quality of fabric dye using Bignay was improved using Treatment 3. The findings suggested that Treatment 3 is more effective than other treatments in producing high-quality of dyed fabric.

Table 8. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Achuete in terms of Rubbing Fastness (Warp and Weft Direction) using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	3.93	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	3.83	Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	4.02	Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.94	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.56	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	3.62	Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	3.58	Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.50	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.20	Highly Acceptable

10. Resistance to Fading.	4.29	Highly Acceptable
11. Resistance to Staining.	4.23	Highly Acceptable
12. Negligible Change.	4.22	Highly Acceptable

Table 8 presents the level of satisfaction of respondents with dyed fabric using achuete in terms of rubbing fastness. The respondents had the same level of satisfaction in Treatment 1 and 2 with mean ratings from 3.50 to 4.02 or “Acceptable.”

Table 8 further revealed that Treatment 3 is more effective than Treatments 1 (1) and 2 (2) with the highest mean ratings from 4.20 to 4.29 or “Highly Acceptable.” The results imply that the quality of dyed fabric using Achuete was improved after the third treatment. Hence, it is highly recommended for producing high-quality dyed fabric using the third treatment of Achuete.

Table 9. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Coconut in terms of Rubbing Fastness (Warp and Weft Direction) using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	3.68	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	3.72	Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	3.58	Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.71	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.48	Acceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	3.53	Acceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	3.39	Moderately Acceptable
3. Negligible Change.	3.47	Acceptable
Treatment 3	1.92	Unacceptable
13. Resistance to Fading.	1.85	Unacceptable
14. Resistance to Staining.	1.97	Unacceptable
15. Negligible Change.	1.87	Unacceptable

Table 9 presents the acceptability level of respondents in producing dyed fabric using coconut in terms of rubbing fastness in Treatments 1, 2, and 3.

The table revealed that Treatments 1 and 2 were recommended for the rubbing fastness of coconut-dyed fabric. However, the third treatment was not acceptable by the respondents in terms of its rubbing fastness.

Table 10. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bankoro in terms of Rubbing Fastness (Warp and Weft Direction) using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Treatment 1	1.51	Highly Unacceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	1.56	Highly Unacceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	1.47	Highly Unacceptable
3. Negligible Change.	1.51	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 2	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
1. Resistance to Fading.	1.43	Highly Unacceptable
2. Resistance to Staining.	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
3. Negligible Change.	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 3	2.00	Unacceptable
16. Resistance to Fading.	2.43	Unacceptable
17. Resistance to Staining.	2.00	Unacceptable
18. Negligible Change.	2.00	Unacceptable

Table 10 reveals that the rubbing fastness of the Bankoro was not appropriate to the acceptability of the respondents. These were based on the mean ratings from 1.00 to 1.56 or “Highly Unacceptable” and 2.00 to 2.43 or “Unacceptable”. Hence, the Bankoro was not highly recommended for the dyed fabric.

Table 11. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Mango in terms of Usefulness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	4.43	Highly Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	4.44	Highly Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	4.38	Highly Acceptable
3. Export potential	4.47	Highly Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.43	Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	2.94	Moderately Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	3.60	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.73	Acceptable
Treatment 3	3.69	Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	3.47	Acceptable

2. Usable for clothing and other related products	3.78	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.80	Acceptable

Table 11 presents the acceptability level of dyed fabric using mango in terms of its usefulness using different treatments. The results revealed that the respondents had the highest level of satisfaction on the quality of dyed fabric of Treatment 1 with mean ratings from 4.38 to 4.44 or "Highly Acceptable." Hence, the results indicated that Treatment 1 was the most effective among treatments.

Table 12. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bignay in terms of Usefulness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.86	Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	3.69	Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	3.98	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.90	Acceptable
Treatment 2	4.03	Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	4.09	Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	4.08	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.84	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.72	Highly Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	4.69	Highly Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	4.80	Highly Acceptable
3. Export potential	4.68	Highly Acceptable

Table 12 further showed that the dyed fabric of Bignay in terms of utility was enhanced after employing the third treatment. The respondents had the same degree of acceptability in treatments 1 and 2, with mean ratings from 3.69 to 4.09 or "Acceptable." Because of its usefulness, the Bignay was generally endorsed by the respondents for generating high-quality dyed fabric.

Table 13. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Achuete in terms of Usefulness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	4.02	Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	4.03	Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	4.03	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.92	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.40	Moderately Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	2.96	Moderately Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	3.55	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.75	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.26	Highly Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	4.40	Highly Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	4.30	Highly Acceptable
3. Export potential	4.18	Highly Acceptable

The third treatment enhanced the utility of the achuete-based colored cloth. The responders generally agreed that the quality of the Achuete-dyed fabric was acceptable. However, they had the highest degree of acceptance in Treatment 3, which suggests that Achuete's Treatment 3 could be able to generate high-quality, usefully colored cloth.

Table 14. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Coconut in terms of Usefulness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.53	Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	3.33	Moderately Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	3.62	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.71	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.38	Moderately Acceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	3.12	Moderately Acceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	3.43	Acceptable
3. Export potential	3.48	Acceptable

Treatment 3	2.00	Unacceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	2.04	Unacceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	1.98	Unacceptable
3. Export potential	1.88	Unacceptable

According to Table 14, respondents' levels of acceptance for each method of treating coconut to produce colorful cloth varied. Treatment 1 generally had the highest mean rating of 3.53, or "Acceptable," suggesting that it was more successful than other treatments. Treatments 2 and 3 did not increase the efficiency of cloth colored with coconut.

Table 15. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bankoro in terms of Usefulness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	1.52	Highly Unacceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	1.53	Highly Unacceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	1.56	Highly Unacceptable
3. Export potential	1.46	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 2	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	1.29	Highly Unacceptable
3. Export potential	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 3	2.00	Unacceptable
1. Blends very efficiently with the fabric	2.00	Unacceptable
2. Usable for clothing and other related products	2.29	Unacceptable
3. Export potential	2.00	Unacceptable

Treatment 3 was improved; however, the findings suggest that utilizing Bankoro was not acceptable based on the respondents' criteria. Table 15 demonstrates that the respondents had the same degree of acceptance of Bankoro in terms of its effectiveness, with mean scores from 1.00 to 1.56 or "Highly Unacceptable."

Table 16. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Mango in terms of Eco-friendliness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	4.39	Highly Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	4.21	Highly Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	4.65	Highly Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	4.34	Highly Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	4.37	Highly Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	4.40	Highly Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.78	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.82	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.79	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.83	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	3.93	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.38	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment 3	3.80	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.78	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.84	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.89	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	3.88	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.52	Acceptable

Table 16 revealed that Treatment 1 was highly recommended in producing high quality of dyed fabric using mango. These were based on the mean ratings from 4.21 to 4.65 or "Highly Acceptable." On the other hand, generally, the respondents had the same level of satisfaction using Treatment 2 and Treatment 3.

Table 17. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bignay in terms of Eco-friendliness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.90	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.92	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.83	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.94	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	4.00	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.65	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.90	Acceptable

1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.88	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.91	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.82	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	3.79	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.93	Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.73	Highly Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	4.72	Highly Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	4.68	Highly Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	4.61	Highly Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	4.60	Highly Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	4.77	Highly Acceptable

Table 17 shows that respondents had the same level of satisfaction with the eco-friendliness of bignay in producing quality dyed fabric using Treatments 1 and 2. Table 17 further revealed that respondents had the highest level of satisfaction using Treatment 3. Hence, they highly recommended the quality of Bignay's dyed fabric in terms of eco-friendliness using Treatment 3.

Table 18. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Achuete in terms of Eco-friendliness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.87	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.89	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.86	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.82	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	3.86	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.97	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.79	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.87	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.91	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.85	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	3.92	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.39	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.14	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	4.18	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	4.25	Highly Acceptable

3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	4.18	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	4.22	Highly Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	4.28	Highly Acceptable

Table 19 indicates that respondents had comparable acceptability in the quality of dyed fabric using Achuete, particularly using different treatments. The table also revealed that in Treatment 3 the respondents highly recommended the achuete because of its sustainability, not disintegrating fabric material, environment safety, and shelf life.

Table 19. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Coconut in terms of Eco-friendliness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.77	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.75	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.82	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.78	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	3.73	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.74	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.59	Acceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	3.58	Acceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	3.62	Acceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	3.62	Acceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	3.55	Acceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	3.42	Acceptable
Treatment 3	1.78	Highly Unacceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	1.76	Highly Unacceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	1.69	Highly Unacceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	1.74	Highly Unacceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	1.85	Highly Unacceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	1.99	Unacceptable

Table 19 reveals that Treatments 1 and 2 of using coconut were acceptable to produce dyed fabric with quality. However, the respondents did not accept the quality of dyed fabric using Treatment 3 of coconut.

Table 20. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bankoro in terms of Eco-friendliness using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	1.49	Highly Unacceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	1.52	Highly Unacceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	1.53	Highly Unacceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	1.48	Highly Unacceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	1.57	Highly Unacceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	1.48	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 2	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	1.31	Highly Unacceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 3	2.00	Unacceptable
1. Dye Odor and toxicity	2.00	Unacceptable
2. Dye products' sustainability	2.00	Unacceptable
3. Dye products do not disintegrate fabric material	2.31	Unacceptable
4. Dye product environmental safety	2.00	Unacceptable
5. Dye products' shelf life	2.00	Unacceptable

The respondents had the same level of acceptability in the eco-friendliness of Bankoro in making dyed fabric. The results revealed that the respondents were not satisfied with the quality of Bankoro in producing dyed fabric.

Table 21. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Mango in terms of Marketability Level using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	4.30	Highly Acceptable
1. Price	4.34	Highly Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	4.26	Highly Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	4.29	Highly Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.50	Acceptable
1. Price	3.62	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.47	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.39	Acceptable
Treatment 3	3.62	Acceptable
1. Price	3.70	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.56	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.53	Acceptable

Table 21 reveals that the respondents had the highest acceptability of Treatment 1 of dyed fabric made from mango in terms of marketability level. On the other hand, the respondents had the same level of acceptability in using Treatments 2 and 3. These results imply that Treatment 1 was more effective than other treatments in terms of marketability level.

Table 22. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bignay in terms of Marketability Level using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.72	Acceptable
1. Price	3.73	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.65	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.71	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.82	Acceptable
1. Price	4.12	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.83	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.60	Acceptable

Treatment 3	4.56	Highly Acceptable
1. Price	4.70	Highly Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	4.37	Highly Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	4.43	Highly Acceptable

Table 22 indicates that respondents had similar acceptability of Bignay dyed fabric in terms of marketability level using Treatments 1 and 2. On the other hand, the respondents gave the highest mean ratings from 4.37 to 4.70 or “Highly Acceptability” which implies that Treatment 3 is the most effective in making dyed fabric of bignay in terms of marketability level.

Table 23. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Achuete in terms of Marketability Level using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.79	Acceptable
1. Price	3.95	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.75	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.70	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.48	Acceptable
1. Price	3.67	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.46	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.32	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment 3	4.23	Highly Acceptable
1. Price	4.24	Highly Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	4.23	Highly Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	4.35	Highly Acceptable

Table 23 reveals that respondents had comparable acceptability levels in Treatments 1 and 2 except for one indicator with a mean rating of 3.32 or “Moderately Acceptable.” This means that the respondents had moderate agreement in the acceptability level of Treatment mainly that the product was safe as compared to other commercially available dyes.

On the other hand, the respondents were highly recommended the Treatment 3 in producing high quality of dyed fabric using Atchuete.

Table 24. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Coconut in terms of Marketability Level using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	3.72	Acceptable
1. Price	3.73	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.66	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.74	Acceptable
Treatment 2	3.44	Acceptable
1. Price	3.46	Acceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.42	Acceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	3.44	Acceptable
Treatment 3	1.94	Unacceptable
1. Price	1.98	Unacceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	1.89	Unacceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	1.94	Unacceptable

Table 24 reveals that the respondents perceived that Treatments 1 and 2 were effective in producing coconut-dyed fabric since they had the same level of acceptability with mean ratings from 3.42 to 3.73 or “Acceptable.”

On the other hand, the respondents do not recommend the coconut-dyed fabric using Treatment 3 based on the mean ratings from 1.89 to 1.98 or “Unacceptable.”

Table 25. Acceptability of Dyed Fabric using Bankoro in terms of Marketability Level using Treatment 1, Treatment 2, and Treatment 3.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Treatment 1	1.48	Highly Unacceptable
1. Price	1.53	Highly Unacceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	1.53	Highly Unacceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	1.42	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 2	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
1. Price	1.00	Highly Unacceptable

2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	1.00	Highly Unacceptable
Treatment 3	2.00	Unacceptable
1. Price	2.00	Unacceptable
2. Product quality (compared to commercially available dyes)	2.00	Unacceptable
3. Product safety (compared to commercially available dyes)	2.00	Unacceptable

Table 25 reveals that the respondents had comparable satisfaction with the quality of bankoro-dyed fabric particularly Treatments 1 and 2. These were based on the mean ratings from 1.00 to 1.53 or “Highly Unacceptable.”

On the other hand, the respondents perceived that Treatment 3 improved the quality of Bankoro dyed fabric, however, still the quality of bankoro dyed fabric was not acceptable.

Table 26. Differences in the Acceptability Level in using different fruits according to their characteristics.

Fruits	Appearance		Rubbing Fastness (Warp and Weft Direction)		Usefulness		Eco-friendliness		Marketability Level	
	Mean	Desc	Mean	Desc	Mean	Desc	Mean	Desc	Mean	Desc
Mango	4.06	A	3.18	MA	3.85	A	3.99	A	3.80	A
Bignay	4.07	A	4.13	A	4.22	HA	4.18	A	4.03	A
Atchuete	3.93	A	3.90	A	3.89	A	3.93	A	3.84	A
Coconut	3.01	MA	3.03	MA	2.97	MA	3.04	MA	3.03	MA
Bankoro	1.51	HU	1.50	HU	1.51	HU	1.50	HU	1.49	HU
<i>Kruskal Wallis H</i>	1063.22*		996.56*		1038.13*		1037.10*		957.10*	
<i>Sig</i>	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	

A=Acceptable MA=Moderately Acceptable HA=Highly Acceptable HU=Highly Unacceptable
*Significant

Table 26 shows the difference in the acceptability of respondents in the different fruits in terms of appearance, rubbing fastness (warp and weft direction), usefulness, eco-friendliness, and marketability level.

In terms of “Appearance”, the Kruskal Wallis H of 1063.22 with a significance level of less than 0.05 indicated that there was significantly different satisfaction in producing dyed fabric using mango, bignay, atchuete, coconut, and bankoro. The results imply that the respondents accepted the appearance of fabric using mango, bignay, and achuete. The respondents gave significantly the highest mean rating of the dyed fabric made from bignay. Hence, they most likely recommended the appearance of bignay in producing dyed fabric. On the other hand, the respondents were highly unacceptable in the appearance of Bankoro in producing a dyed fabric with a mean rating of 1.51.

In terms of “Rubbing Fastness (warp and weft direction)”, the Kruskal Wallis H value of 996.56 with a significance level less than 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This result indicated that significantly different level of satisfaction in the rubbing fastness of using different types of fruits in producing dyed fabric. Furthermore, the table revealed that using Bignay is highly recommended in terms of its rubbing fastness. On the other hand, the Bankoro had the lowest mean rating of 1.50 or “Highly Acceptable.”

In terms of “Usefulness”, the Kruskal Wallis H value of 1038.13 with a significance level of less than 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These imply that there was a significantly different level of acceptability in producing dyed fabric using mango, bignay, achuete, coconut, and bankoro. The respondents gave the significantly highest mean rating of 4.22 or “Highly Acceptable” for the dyed fabric made of Bignay. Hence, they most likely recommended the usefulness of Bignay in producing dyed fabric. On the other hand, the respondents were highly unacceptable the Bankoro in producing dyed fabric.

In terms of “Eco-friendliness”, the Kruskal Wallis H value of 1037.10 with a significance level of less than 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis implying that there was a significant difference in the acceptability level of dyed fabric using different types of fruits. The table further revealed that the respondents most likely recommended the Bignay in producing dyed fabric. On the other hand, the respondents gave the lowest mean rating of 1.50 or “Highly Unacceptable.”

In terms of “Marketability Level”, the Kruskal Wallis H value of 957.10 with a significance level of less than 0.05 implies that there was a significant difference in the level of acceptability of dyed fabric using different types. The dyed fabric made from Bignay was most likely recommended to the producers based on the mean rating of 4.03 or “Acceptable”. On the other hand, the Bankoro had the lowest mean rating of 1.49 or “Highly Unacceptable.”

Table 27. Post Hoc Analysis in the Difference of Acceptability Level of Fruits

Pairs	Appearance		Rubbing Fastness (Warp and Weft Direction)		Usefulness		Eco-friendliness		Marketability Level	
	Z	Sig	Z	Sig	Z	Sig	Z	Sig	Z	Sig
Mango and Bignay	23.42*	0.00	18.93*	0.00	23.59*	0.00	19.82*	0.00	21.50*	0.00
Mango and Atchuete	23.46*	0.00	20.66*	0.00	23.65*	0.00	23.08*	0.00	22.34*	0.00
Mango and Coconut	1.09 ^{ns}	0.27	3.60*	0.00	20.97*	0.00	13.22*	0.00	15.39*	0.00
Mango and Bankoro	6.81*	0.00	4.77*	0.00	21.15*	0.00	22.51*	0.00	14.33*	0.00
Bignay and Atchuete	1.19 ^{ns}	0.23	3.06*	0.00	0.84*	0.40	11.65*	0.00	7.25*	0.00
Bignay and Coconut	23.47*	0.00	17.79*	0.00	23.73*	0.00	22.70*	0.00	21.28*	0.00
Bignay and Bankoro	23.40*	0.00	17.50*	0.00	23.67*	0.00	23.34*	0.00	21.59*	0.00

Atchuete and Coconut	23.52*	0.00	19.29*	0.00	23.82*	0.00	23.42*	0.00	23.11*	0.00
Atchuete Bankoro	23.45*	0.00	18.96*	0.00	23.78*	0.00	23.42*	0.00	23.12*	0.00
Coconut and Bankoro	6.15*	0.00	1.08 ^{ns}	0.28	1.17*	0.24	19.78*	0.00	2.65*	0.01

*Significant nsNot Significant

Table 27 shows the post hoc analysis in the difference of acceptability level of fruits according to their characteristics. The researcher used Bonferroni correction for post hoc analysis with new significance level of 0.01.

In terms of appearance of different fruits, the Z values from 6.15 to 23.52 with significance levels less than 0.01 led to the rejection of null hypothesis indicating that the respondents had statistically significant difference in each pair of fruits except mango and coconut, and bignay and atchuete. These imply that the respondents had similar agreement in the appearance of these pairs of fruits. On the other hand, the respondents were more likely agreed about the appearance of bignay compared to mango, atchuete, coconut, and bankoro. Furthermore, the respondents were more likely agreed in the appearance of Bignay compared to Achuete, Coconut, and Bankoro. The respondents were more likely perceived the acceptance of Achuete than Coconut and Bankoro.

In terms of rubbing fastness, the Z values from 3.06 to 20.66 with significance levels less than 0.01 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis indicating that the respondents had statistically significant difference in each pair of fruits except Coconut and Bankoro. These imply that the respondents had comparable acceptability level in the rubbing fastness of Coconut and Bankoro.

In terms of usefulness, the Z values from 20.97 to 23.82 with significance levels less than 0.01 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis indicating that the respondents' acceptability level had statistically significant in each pair of fruits except Bignay and Achuete, and Coconut and Bankoro. The respondents imply that these fruits had similar level of acceptability in their usefulness.

In terms of eco-friendliness, the results revealed the Z values from 12.65 to 23.42 with significance levels less than 0.01 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis stating that the respondents' acceptability level had statistically significant difference in each pair of fruits.

Lastly, in terms of marketability level, the results revealed the Z values from 11.65 to 23.12 with significance levels less than 0.01 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis stating that the respondents' acceptability level had statistically significant difference in each pair of fruits.

Generally, the results revealed that the respondents had the highest acceptability level in using Bignay in producing quality of dyed fabric in terms of appearance, rubbing fastness, usefulness, eco-friendliness, and marketability level.

Table 28. Difference in the Acceptability Level in using different fruits according to type of respondents

Fruits	Respondents						Kruskal Wallis H	Sig
	Students		Instructors		Others			
	Mean	Desc	Mean	Desc	Mean	Desc		
Mango	2.98	MA	2.75	MA	2.72	MA	60.02*	0.00
Bignay	3.80	A	3.94	A	3.90	A	3.27 ^{ns}	0.20
Achuete	4.02	A	4.03	A	3.97	A	2.61 ^{ns}	0.27
Coconut	3.50	A	3.55	A	3.55	A	1.78 ^{ns}	0.41
Bankoro	2.55	UN	2.93	MA	2.95	MA	2.54 ^{ns}	0.28

HA=Highly Acceptable A=Acceptable MA=Moderately Acceptable HU=Highly Unacceptable
*Significant

Table 28 presents the difference in the acceptability level in using different fruits according to type of respondents. The table revealed that F values from 1.78 to 3.27 with significance levels greater than 0.05 led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. These results imply that the respondents had comparable acceptability level in the quality of Bignay, Achuete, Coconut and Bankoro in producing dyed fabric.

On the other hand, the respondents had significantly different acceptability in using mango to make dyed fabric. The students most likely uncertain the quality of mango for dyed fabric with a highest mean rating of 2.98 or “Moderate Acceptable.”

Table 29. Post hoc Analysis using Bonferroni Correction

Pairs	Z	Sig
Students - Instructors	6.13*	0.00
Instructors-Others	1.12 ^{ns}	0.26
Students-Others	6.41*	0.00
*Significant ns Not Significant		

Table 29 displays the post hoc analysis using Bonferroni Correction in the difference of acceptability of mango according to the respondents. The results revealed that students and instructors, and students and others had statistically significant acceptability level in producing dyed fabric made from mango. These were based on the Z values of 6.13 and 6.41 with probability levels of p=0.00.

Table 30. Overall Assessment in the difference of dyed fabric using different fruits.

Fruits	Mean	Overall Desc	Kruskal Wallis H	Sig
Mango	3.78	Acceptable		
Bignay	4.13	Acceptable		
Achuete	3.90	Acceptable	1057.37*	0.00
Coconut	3.02	Moderately Acceptable		
Bankoro	1.50	Highly Unacceptable		

*Significant

Table 30 presents the overall assessment of respondents in the acceptability level of dyed fabric using different fruits. The Kruskal Wallis H value of 1057.37 with significance level less than 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis implying that there was significantly satisfaction level of dyed fabric using different fruits. The table further revealed that the respondents were highly recommended the Bignay in making dyed fabric. On the other hand, the Bankoro had the lowest mean rating of 1.50 or “Highly Unacceptable” implying that respondents were least likely not recommended the quality of Bankoro in making dyed fabric.

Table 30. Post Hoc Analysis in the Difference of Acceptability Level of Fruits.

Pairs	Over-all	
	Z	Sig
Mango and Bignay	22.69*	0.00
Mango and Atchuete	23.24*	0.00
Mango and Coconut	22.99*	0.00
Mango and Bankoro	16.27*	0.00
Bignay and Atchuete	4.61*	0.00
Bignay and Coconut	12.34*	0.00
Bignay and Bankoro	21.15*	0.00
Atchuete and Coconut	19.51*	0.00
Atchuete and Bankoro	23.21*	0.00
Coconut and Bankoro	20.91*	0.00

*Significant

Table 30 displays the post hoc analysis in the over-all assessment of fruits in producing dyed fabric. The researcher used Bonferroni Correction with significance levels less than 0.01. The Z values from 4.61 to 23.24 with significance levels less than 0.01 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis implying that each pair of fruits had statistically significant difference. Based from the computed mean in Table 29, the respondents were most likely had the highest acceptability level in using Bignay for dyed fabric.

Table 31. Effect Sizes of Dyed Fabric using different fruits.

Criteria	Eta Squared (η^2)	Verbal Description
Mango	0.327	Large
Bignay	0.488	Large
Achuete	0.366	Large
Coconut	0.458	Large
Bankoro	0.303	Large

The table above presents the size effect of the dyed fabric using different fruits. The effect sizes from 0.303 to 0.488 or described as “Large”, indicated that the fruits in making dyed fabric have large effect sizes after using treatments whose aim is to refine the quality of dyed fabric. Overall, there was a large effect size of 0.488 implying that there was a biggest effect of using Bignay to improve the quality of dyed fabric.

Conclusions

This study concludes that natural dyeing agents derived from indigenous fruits, such as mango, bignay, and achuete, have significant potential for producing high-quality dyed fabrics. The findings indicate that certain treatments, particularly those utilizing mango and bignay, yielded "Highly Acceptable" ratings in terms of colorfastness, appearance, and overall satisfaction among respondents. The acceptability of dyed fabrics varied across different treatments, with Treatment 1 of mango and Treatment 3 of bignay being particularly favored for their superior qualities, including brightness, vibrancy, and eco-friendliness. In contrast, the use of *bankoro* was largely deemed unacceptable, highlighting the necessity for careful selection of natural dye sources. Furthermore, the statistically significant differences in acceptability levels across various fruits underscore the importance of employing rigorous testing to identify optimal dyeing methods. The implications of these findings suggest that utilizing indigenous fruits not only supports local agricultural practices but also promotes sustainable and eco-friendly textile production. This research lays the groundwork for further exploration into the commercial viability of natural dyes, advocating for their integration into the textile industry as a means to enhance both product quality and environmental sustainability. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for continued innovation in natural dyeing techniques to fully realize their potential in the market.

Recommendations

In view of the above conclusions, this study recommends the following:

1. Teachers are encouraged to embrace innovative teaching strategies that incorporate natural dyes into the curriculum, allowing students to experiment with these materials

in art and science projects while fostering creativity and understanding of sustainable practices.

2. Advocating for the integration of natural dye studies in school programs should be a priority for school heads, who can organize workshops and training sessions for teachers to effectively convey the significance of natural dyes in environmental sustainability.
3. Collaboration opportunities with educational institutions should be explored by industry workers to promote the use of natural dyes in textile and craft industries, adopting eco-friendly practices that benefit the environment and appeal to a growing market for sustainable products.
4. Parents play a crucial role in supporting their children's learning about natural dyes by engaging in hands-on activities, such as dyeing fabrics with natural materials at home, which can deepen their appreciation for sustainability and enhance their connection to nature.
5. Continuing to investigate the benefits and applications of natural dyes should be a focus for researchers, as their findings can contribute to a broader understanding of sustainable practices and inspire future innovations in eco-friendly products.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research followed ethical standards and adhered to principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility towards the participants. Before conducting the study, the researcher obtained informed consent from the participants. She ensured that they understood the purpose of the study, its procedures, and potential risks. Confidentiality and anonymity were well kept up throughout data collection, analysis, and dissemination, safeguarding participants' privacy. Additionally, the researcher made sure that there was no conflict of interest in conducting the study, avoided plagiarism issues, and no bias was made in the interpretation of the results of the study. Finally, she ensured that the findings were used only for the research.

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REFERENCES

- Ahsan, R., Masood, A., Sherwani, R., & Khushbakhat, H. (2020). Extraction and Application of Natural Dyes on Natural Fibers: An Eco-Friendly Perspective. *Review of Education, Administration & LAW*.
- Ayele, M., Tesfaye, T., Alemu, D., Limeneh, M., & Sithole, B.B. (2020). Natural dyeing of cotton fabric with extracts from mango tree: A step towards sustainable dyeing. *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy*, 17, 100293.

- Dhanania, Y., Singhee, D., & Samanta, A.K. (2021). Optimization of dyeing process variables for eco-friendly dyeing of cotton fabric with babul bark extract as a natural dye and gallnut extract as a bio-mordant. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 19, 5478 - 5495.
- Jabar, J.M., Owokotomo, I.A., & Ogunsade, A.F. (2022). Sustainable dyeing of cotton fabric with mangiferin: Roles of microwave-rays and bio-mordants on fabric colorimetric and fastness properties. *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy*.
- Kasim, K.F., Ghafar, N.A., & Abdul Kadir, N. (2023). Optimization of Natural Dye Extraction from Coconut Husk. *International Journal of Biomass Utilization and Sustainable Energy (IJBUSE)*.
- Kholil, A.S., Adani, H.U., Mufsihah, A., & Chafidz, A. (2021). Utilization of Old Coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) Husk Waste as Potential Source of Natural Dye and its Dyeing Properties on Cotton Cloth. *Key Engineering Materials*, 882, 280 - 286.
- Loum, J., Byamukama, R., & Wanyama, P.A. (2021). Application of natural dyes from selected indigenous plants on cotton and silk fabrics. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*.
- Putri, S.A., Andriana, Y.F., & Septiana, U. (2020). EKPLORASI PENGOLAHAN SERAT SABUT KELAPA DENGAN PEWARNA ALAMI SECANG SEBAGAI MATERIAL ALTERNATIF FURNITUR.
- Savvidou, M., & Economides, D. (2007). Colour gamut produced by applying mixtures of natural dyes on de-inked mechanical pulp. *Coloration Technology*, 123, 119-123.
- Tamburini, D., Klink-Hoppe, Z., & McCarthy, B. (2024). New insights into the dyes of Central Asian ikat textiles. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*.
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